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A Study on Attitude of Pre-Service Secondary Teachers toward Human Rights Education and Peace Education.

Sony Dupak¹, TageAmpa²

¹Research Scholar, Department of Education, Rajiv Gandhi University, A.P.

²Assistant Professor, Department of Education, Dera Natung Government College, Itanagar

Abstract

The investigators conducted a study to know the attitude towards Human Rights Education and Peace Education of pre-service secondary teachers of Department of Education, Rajiv Gandhi University, Hills College of Teacher Education and Donyi-Polo B.Ed College Itanagar, Arunachal Pradesh. For this purposes, normative survey method of research was used. A sample consists of 50 pre-service teachers were selected randomly. Peace Education and Human Rights Education Attitude scale for pre-service teachers developed by Dr. Jayadeba Sahoo, Professor, Department of Education, Rajiv Gandhi University, Rono Hills were used for data collection. Mean (M), standard deviation (SD), and t-test were used to analyze the data. The attitude of both male and female were analyzed. The findings revealed that no significant difference was found in the attitude level of male and female pre-service teachers. The authors stressed on imparting peace education and human rights education in college. Knowledge of human rights education makes students better able to participate in society and encourages pre-service teachers to think broadly when they plan to teach for peace.

KEYWORDS : *Peace Education, Human Rights Education, pre-service teachers.*

Introduction:-

Human rights education and peace education are closely linked activities that complement and support each other. Peace is a fundamental pre-condition without which rights cannot be realized, while at the same time, the ensuring of basic rights is essential to bringing about peace. Human rights education (HRE) is an emergent field of educational theory and practice gaining increased attention and significance across the globe. The international human rights movement, spurred by the efforts of non-governmental organizations, the United Nations and other regional human rights bodies, has broadened its focus since the late 1970s, by seeking to integrate human rights concepts, norms and values within the mainstream educational systems of world states. Education for peace is not a slogan or catchword that has been coined recently, but more precisely it emerged as a trend an urgent call of world community around First World War. People realized that it is only education which can help in regaining peace in the world after the catastrophe of war. Since then, various efforts have been made to bring peace through education. But over the years, peace education is gaining more and more importance all over the world. It is mainly because of the increase in the rate of violence, terrorism, wars and conflicts

in all the societies of the world. It can be noted that though there has been tremendous advances in science and technology, the dawn of the new millennium have witnessed violence, terrorism, drug abuse, war and conflicts all over the world. Hence, integrating peace education and human rights education in the curriculum has become an urgent need today. In today's world child spends most of its time at school. Therefore nurturing the child holistically is the responsibility of the teacher. The teacher helps the students acquire knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed to bring changes in their behavior. But in order to teach the students, the teacher himself has to have a positive attitude towards human rights education and peace education. Having awareness and positive attitude towards human rights education and peace education amongst teachers is very important to develop peace, values and knowledge in the minds of students. So, that researchers have taken this study to know the attitude of pre service teacher regarding peace education and human rights education because they are the upcoming teachers of the nation. Peace is a global concept and every individual has to be filled with peace for both physical and mental health. It is also a value to be cherished from birth till death. The dictionary meaning of peace is "A State of Quiet, Freedom from Contention, Ease of Mind or Conscience, Tranquillity, Quiet, Stillness and Silence". The meaning is quite comprehensive and each of the individual meanings given deserves detailed discussion and explanation. Peace does not mean an absence of war or conflict alone. It has something to do with the mind and attitude of people. In the deepest sense, peace is a sense of goodwill towards others, wishing them the best in life. According to Federico Mayor, 'Peace is possible for life at all stages and it is up to man to choose his destiny or to suffer from the horrors of war. Today mankind is at the cross-road where he/she has to choose with courage, determination and imagination. Peace education is a broader discipline and has been defined in many ways. There is no universally accepted definition as such. Generally, peace education aims at teaching individuals the information, attitude, values and behavioral competencies needed to resolve conflicts without violence and to build and maintain mutually beneficial, harmonious relationships. John Dewey (1938) explained that "peace education is grounded in active citizenship, preparing learners for audacious participation in a democracy through problem posing and problem solving education, and a commitment to transformative action in our society." Peace is a vital condition of human rights to be practiced completely and forms the foundation of human rights. For this reason, it is obligatory to think human rights education together with peace education (Kamaraj&Aktan, 2005).

Human rights and basic freedoms are the individual rights which are resulted from humanely needs and skills (Beetham& Boyle, 1998, 99). Human rights cannot be taken away; no one has the right to deprive another person of them for any reason. Human rights are inalienable and they are inherent to each individual. It is impossible to have dignified and humane life without human rights (Uygun, 1996, 7). The primary way to obtain real respect to human rights is to educate human rights. It is impossible to get the respect to human rights by means of the mechanisms of control and protection alone. Because they can be only operated after violating the rules of human rights (Gülmez, 1996, 1). The education of human rights is an effective way of work in making people aware of their own rights in order to defense universal values in the national and advanced level (Yeşil, 2002, 45). In a number of countries, efforts are underway

to upgrade the quality of pre-service teacher education. Training may include a focus on such skills as the use of interactive and participatory teaching methods, organizing cooperative group work, and facilitating group discussions. The use of these types of teaching methods is essential to quality basic education, and enables pre-service teachers to convey values of cooperation, respect for the opinions of the people, and appreciation of differences. Participatory teaching and learning strategies can be used throughout the curriculum, and are an essential component of efforts to promote peace and human rights through education. Pre-service teacher education in peace and human rights education is an important feature of the programme in India, with one national teacher training college designated as the focal point for the development of pre-service training programmes in peace and human rights education, integrated into each of the traditional subject areas.

Review of related literature:-

Bedir.G and Arslan. M (2013) studied on, The Secondary Education Students' perceptions regarding peace education and human rights. The result stated that there are differences between the students' perceptions on peace education ($U=12920.5$, $p.05$) and the perceptions on human rights according to their sex ($U=16300.0$, $p.05$). When the rank mean is examined it is seen that female students' rank mean is higher than male students'. It may be resulted from the reason that girls are more sensitive than boys.

Gundogdu.K(2010) studied on The effect of constructivist instruction on prospective teachers attitudes towards human rights education. The results show that the use of both constructivist teaching and learning activities and traditional methods increased the prospective teachers' degree of appreciation for human rights education. However, the use of constructivist methods and materials in the human rights course had more positive impact on the students' teachers' attitudes towards human rights.

Houten.V and Santner.V (2010) studied on, Youth as Actors in Peace and Human Rights Education Youth is a heterogeneous group with multiple needs, (political) ideas and capacities which are important for the successfulness of pro-peace and development processes. Research and practice shows that youth are often the primary producers of violence in the period after the signing of the peace accords, because: 1) Youth victims of violence have learned using violence is a way to approach conflicts. 2) There is a lack of alternatives for former combatants. 3) Political exclusion and marginalization of youth during and after peace and development processes leads to frustration among youth. 4) Of the thin lines between politically active youth and youth criminality (McEvoy-Levy 2001:10-14).

Sharma. V and Jain. S (2012) studied on 'Peace education and human rights in twenty first century: A review and it could be helpful to think that "practicing peace" begins with a search for "inner peace". The search for "inner peace" has captured the imagination of many people today; particularly it seems in western societies where alienation and disaffection seem to sit uneasily alongside unprecedented levels of material possession and consumption. Thus, students need to be respectful and open- minded without being uncritically tolerant and accept-

ing. They need to be cooperative and empathetic while still being assertive.

Review of the related study provides a strong background for initiating an investigation about human rights education, peace education and gender among Pre-service teacher at the secondary level. The review helped in locating comparative data useful in the interpretation of results.

Objectives of the study.

The following are the objective of the study.

1. To study the attitude of peace education among male and female pre-service secondary teachers of Papumpare District Arunachal Pradesh.
2. To study the attitude of human rights education among male and female pre-service secondary teachers of Papumpare District Arunachal Pradesh.

Hypotheses of the study:-

Hypotheses of the present study are as follows:

1. There is no significant difference between male and female pre-service secondary teachers towards peace education in Papumpare District of Arunachal Pradesh.
2. There is no significant difference between male and female pre-service secondary teachers towards human rights education in Papumpare District of Arunachal Pradesh.

Design of the study:

The present study was conducted to study the attitude of the pre-service secondary teachers of B.Ed College towards the human rights education and peace education. For this purpose, normative survey method of research was employed in the present investigation.

Sample of the study:

The samples were selected using the random sampling technique. It comprised of 50 pre-service secondary teachers of Department of Education, Rajiv Gandhi University, Hills College of Teacher Education and Donyi-Polo B.Ed College, Itanagar, Papumpare District of Arunachal Pradesh. It was divided into male and female, pre-service secondary teachers.

Tools used:

The following tools were used to collect the relevant data.

1. Attitude scale to measure the pre-service teachers towards human rights education developed by Prof. J. Sahoo (2006).
2. Attitude scale to measure the pre-service teachers towards peace education developed by Prof. J. Sahoo (2015).

Statistical techniques used:

For analysis of data statistical techniques like Mean, standard deviation and t-test were employed.

Analysis & interpretation of results:

Table No.1

Mean scores, Standard deviation, SED and ‘t’ value of male and female pre-service secondary teachers in Papumpare District (AP).

SI/No	Category	N	Mean	Standard-Deviation	SE _D	‘t’value	Remark
1	Male	25	258.2	9.52	2.66	0.67	No Significant
2	Female	25	256.4	9.31			

Table no. 1 shows the mean scores of male and female pre-service secondary teachers of Papumpare District (AP) on attitudes towards Peace Education are 258.2 and 256.4 and standard deviation are 9.52 and 9.31 respectively. The calculated ‘t’ value is 0.67 which is less than the table value of 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance and 2.68 at 0.01 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant difference in attitudes of male and female pre-service secondary teachers towards the peace education in Papumpare District, Arunachal Pradesh is accepted. Hence, it is found that male and female pre-service secondary teachers have equal attitude towards the peace education in Papumpare District of Arunachal Pradesh.

Table No.2

Attitudes towards Human Rights Education Mean scores, Standard deviation, SED and ‘t’ value of male and female pre-service secondary teachers in Papumpare District (AP).

SI No	Category	N	Mean	Standard-Deviation	SE _D	‘t’value	Remark
1.	Male	25	125	9.05	7.039	0.85	No Significant
2	Female	25	119	9.70			

Table no. 2 shows the mean scores of male and female pre-service secondary teachers of Papumpare District (AP) on attitudes towards Human Rights Education are 125 and 119 and standard deviation are 9.05 and 9.70 respectively. The calculated ‘t’ value is 0.85 which is less than the table value of 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance and 2.68 at 0.01 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis of no significant difference in attitudes of male and female of pre-service secondary teachers towards the human rights education in Papumpare District, Arunachal Pradesh is accepted. Hence, it is found that male and female pre-service secondary teachers have equal attitudes towards human rights education in Papumpare District of Arunachal Pradesh.

Conclusions:

From the findings of the study it can be concluded that there is no significant difference in attitudes of male and female pre-service secondary teachers towards the peace education. The investigation on the peace education attitude revealed that the male and female pre-service

secondary teachers have equal attitude towards peace education. It is also found that there is no significant difference in attitudes of male and female pre-service secondary teachers towards human rights education. From this study it is interpreted that the variable sex does not play a significant role in determining Human Rights Education attitude among the pre-service secondary teachers of Papumpare District of Arunachal Pradesh. Thus the study revealed that the male and female pre-service secondary teachers have equal attitude on Human Rights Education. When individuals are unaware of human rights, rights cannot be used properly and it is impossible to process these mechanisms for violation of rights. As a result of this, not also individuals learn their rights, but also they become aware of using them concretely. The violence events confronted in college are the behaviors learned later. Students' (pre-service secondary teachers) lifelong experiments and learning have been realized in their families, environments and schools. From this point of view, it is necessary to inform our students about peace education and human right. Not only it is necessary to have positive opinions and emotions, but also it is vital to turn them into behaviors when they confronted with violent events. As a result of this there can be peaceful and untroubled atmosphere. For this reason, colleges have to prepare Peace Education and Human Rights programs in their syllabus for better attitude and awareness of the trainees. The programme should be implemented as soon as possible so that trainees are equipped with Human Rights and Peace Education.

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